

ASSESSING THE NEXUS BETWEEN ECOWAS TRADE POLICIES AND SECTORAL GDP GROWTH IN NIGERIA

PRINCE OJOCHEGBE AKWU

Department of political science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi
Email: akwu prince@gmail.com, 07032921440

RUTH CALEB LUKA

Department of political science, Nasarawa State University, Keffi
Email: lukaruth81@gmail.com, 08032905189

ABSTRACT

The Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS) has, since its establishment in 1975, drive policies aimed at promoting economic integration and sustainable development across the ECOWAS countries. Among its central objectives is the liberalization of West Africa trade to stimulate sectoral growth and industrial competitiveness among member states. Nigeria, as the largest economy within ECOWAS countries, stands as the center-piece of these regional trade policies. This study critically assesses the nexus between ECOWAS trade policies and sectoral Gross Domestic Product (GDP) growth in Nigeria. It explores how policy instruments such as the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS), and the Protocol on Free Movement of Goods and Persons have influenced key sectors of the Nigerian economy Agriculture, Manufacturing, and Services. Employing a qualitative and descriptive research design anchored in primary and secondary data, the study examines trade trends, policy frameworks, and sectoral responses to ECOWAS integration efforts from 1990 to 2024. The findings reveal a mixed outcome while trade liberalization has fostered modest growth in agriculture and services, structural bottlenecks, policy inconsistency, and infrastructural decay have hindered manufacturing competitiveness. The paper concludes that Nigeria's capacity to maximize the benefits of ECOWAS trade policies depends on institutional reforms, infrastructural investment, and a coherent national trade strategy aligned with regional commitments. Policy recommendations include strengthening local value chains, improving border efficiency, and enhancing macroeconomic coordination to promote sustainable sectoral growth through ECOWAS frameworks.

Keywords: ECOWAS, Trade Policy, Sectoral GDP, Nigeria, Economic Integration.

1. INTRODUCTION

Most countries of the world are primarily concerned with identifying strategies capable of guaranteeing robust economic prosperity. This concern is more pronounced among developing countries, which continuously implement economic policies aimed at boosting output and enhancing competitiveness within the global economy. In this context, regional economic integration has remained a central feature of West Africa's post-colonial development agenda, driven by the need to achieve economic viability and collective self-reliance. One of the most prominent initiatives in this regard is the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS), established to promote sub-regional trade, stimulate industrial growth, and foster economic cooperation among member states through the reduction of trade barriers, tariff harmonization, and the facilitation of the movement of goods, capital, and people.

Nigeria, as the most populous country and the largest economy within ECOWAS, occupies a pivotal position in determining the success or failure of these regional trade initiatives. However, the extent to which trade policies promote economic growth and development remains a subject of intense debate. While the traditional view, as noted by Akpan and Atan

(2017), regards trade as an engine of growth, dissenting perspectives argue that trade can reinforce structural dependence and underdevelopment in poorer economies. The conventional mechanism suggests that international trade enhances income, investment, and technological progress, which in turn improves productivity and competitiveness, creating a virtuous cycle of trade expansion and economic growth. Empirical evidence from the nineteenth and twentieth centuries largely supports this perspective, with trade functioning as an ‘engine’ or ‘elixir’ of growth for many economies (Manni and Afzal, 2012).

Despite these theoretical expectations, the relationship between trade policy and sectoral economic performance is often complex, particularly in developing economies characterized by weak institutions, infrastructural deficits, and macroeconomic instability. Within the ECOWAS framework, trade instruments such as the ECOWAS Trade Liberalization Scheme (ETLS) and the Common External Tariff (CET) were designed to expand market access, improve competitiveness, and stimulate regional trade. In Nigeria, however, the outcomes of these policies have been uneven across sectors. The agricultural sector has benefited from increased regional demand for agro-based products but continues to suffer from poor logistics, inadequate infrastructure, and post-harvest losses. The manufacturing sector, which was expected to gain from expanded regional markets, remains constrained by high production costs, unreliable electricity supply, and competition from imported goods (Sotinwa, 2017). Conversely, the services sector particularly finance and telecommunications has experienced relatively steady growth, benefiting from regional integration and digital trade, while the oil and gas sector continues to dominate Nigeria’s export profile, reflecting limited productive diversification.

Against this backdrop, this study examines the nexus between ECOWAS trade policies and sectoral GDP growth in Nigeria, focusing on how regional trade integration has influenced overall economic performance and sector-specific growth outcomes. The study proceeds on the premise that ECOWAS trade policies exert a generally positive but uneven impact on sectoral GDP growth, and that the extent of these benefits depends largely on the quality of domestic infrastructure, financial access, and institutional coordination. By identifying the structural constraints that limit Nigeria’s gains from ECOWAS trade frameworks, the study also seeks to propose policy measures capable of enhancing sectoral growth and competitiveness within the sub-region.

The significance of this study lies in its contribution to the policy discourse on regional integration and economic development. While much of the existing literature focuses on the effects of ECOWAS on trade volumes or aggregate GDP, limited attention has been given to how individual sectors respond differently to trade policy reforms in Nigeria. By analysing the relationship between ECOWAS trade policies and sectoral GDP growth, this study provides a more nuanced understanding of how regional economic cooperation shapes national development outcomes. The remainder of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 reviews the relevant literature, Section 3 outlines the methodology, Section 4 presents and discusses the empirical findings, and Section 5 concludes with policy implications and recommendations.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Theoretical Literature

Trade policy refers to the set of government regulations and strategies that determine how a country carried out its trade with other countries. According to Sachs and Warner (1995)., trade policy redesigns a country’s trade into the global economy and determines its comparative advantage. In developing nations, trade liberalization policy has been promoted as a mechanism for fostering industrial growth, technology transfer, and economic diversification

(Winters, McCulloch, and McKay, 2004). However, the impact of trade regime on growth rest upon institutional capacity, macroeconomic stability, and sectoral adaptability.

Sectoral GDP represents the diverse contribution of sectional economic sectors such as agriculture, industry, and service to national output. Todaro and Smith (2015) opined, sustained economic development depends not only on overall growth but also on balanced growth across sectors. For instance, in Nigeria, the agricultural sector still maintains the largest employer of labour, while manufacturing is adversely for industrial transformation. Service sector, encompassing finance, telecommunications, and trade, has grown rapidly in recent years, yet structural dependence on oil persists (National Bureau of Statistics (NBS), 2023). Winters et al. (2004) provide strong theoretical justification for examining sectoral outcomes, rather than assuming uniform growth effects across the economy. They opined trade liberalization does not automatically reduce poverty or guarantee broad-based growth; its outcomes depend critically on domestic conditions such as infrastructure, labor mobility, institutional quality, and sectoral structure.

2.2 Empirical Literature

Empirical studies provide evidence on the relationship between trade liberalization and economic growth in Nigeria. Sachs and Warner (1995) found that open economies tend to grow faster than closed ones, while Rodriguez and Rodrik (2000) caution that trade liberalization alone does not guarantee growth without complementary institutional and macroeconomic frameworks. In Sub-Saharan Africa, trade liberalization has had limited success in stimulating industrialization due to infrastructural bottlenecks and weak governance (UNECA, 2017).

These findings are consistent with Ashakah and Akpughe (2021), who reported that ECOWAS economic integration has contributed positively to Nigeria's economic growth but with limited sectoral spillovers, particularly in manufacturing. Similarly, Oloyede, Osabuohien, and Ejemeyovwi (2021), using panel data from ECOWAS and SADC, found that trade openness promotes growth only when supported by strong institutional and infrastructural frameworks. The convergence of these findings suggests that Nigeria's gains from ECOWAS trade policies are conditional rather than automatic.

On the international front, Mkubwa, et al (2014) examined the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth, export, import and inflation in developing countries with a case study of Bangladesh economy between 1980 and 2010. Using ordinary least square technique, the study found that gross domestic product (GDP) is highly influenced by trade liberalization which further suggests that greater openness has had a favourable effect on economic development in the country. Similarly, Mkubwa (2014) analyzed the effect of trade liberalization on economic growth in Tanzania between 1970 and 2010. The authors divided the study period into a closed economy period of 1970-1985 and an open economy period of 1986-2010. The method of ordinary least square was adopted to estimate the regression for the two periods. Findings from the study indicates that trade openness has a positive and significant impact on economic growth for the two periods in Tanzania. Aliyu, (2008) studied the link between openness and growth in the context of sub-Saharan Africa, he estimated cross country growth regression with OLS using a sample of 36 sub-Saharan African countries during two sub periods (1990-2000) and (1995-2000). The limited response of Nigeria's manufacturing sector also aligns with Oddih and Okor (2020), who identified infrastructural deficits, weak industrial base, and policy inconsistencies as major constraints undermining the effectiveness of ECOWAS integration. In the same vein, Adeyele and Ouedraogo (2019) emphasized that weak governance and financial integration in ECOWAS countries reduce the growth-enhancing effects of regional trade agreements. These studies reinforce the present finding that ECOWAS trade liberalization has not sufficiently translated into industrial upgrading in Nigeria.

From the cross-country study he found out that open countries in the region tend to grow faster than those that are closed. Evidence reveals that while in some countries such as (Botswana,

Ghana and Cameroon) open regimes are associated with faster growth rates, while others such as (South Africa and Zambia) open regimes had slower growth rates of output. Therefore, he concluded that the relationship between openness and growth is a contingent one.

Several studies have examined Nigeria's involvement in ECOWAS trade liberalization. Adenikinju & Chete (2002) examined that Nigeria's trade liberalization under ECOWAS trade regime increased cross-border trade but failed to significantly foster manufacturing output as a result of infrastructural challenges. Similarly, Akpan & Atan (2012) observed that the ETLs enhanced agricultural exports but had little effect on industrial diversification. Recent studies by Yusuf (2020) and Ayinde (2021) argued that while Nigeria benefits from market expansion within ECOWAS, poor logistics, border inefficiencies, and policy inconsistency undermine competitiveness.

Although existing literature on ECOWAS trade policies is expanding, there is still no clear consensus on their sector-specific impacts on Nigeria's economy. Much of the current research relies on aggregate analyses that emphasize overall GDP or trade volumes, while giving insufficient attention to differences across economic sectors. In addition, the potential moderating influences of institutional effectiveness, infrastructure capacity, and policy coherence remain largely unexplored. This study therefore addresses an important gap by conducting a sector-level investigation into the relationship between ECOWAS trade policies and Nigeria's economic performance.

3. METHODOLOGY

The research design adopted in this study is case study research design. The use of case study research design, in this study, involves data collection and data analysis on past Assessing the Nexus between ECOWAS Trade Policies and Sectoral GDP Growth in Nigeria with a view to understanding their previous and current efforts in trade policy reforms for better economic development in Nigeria, while at the same time making predictions for the future. The population of the study comprises staffs of the ECOWAS secretariat, Ministry of foreign affairs, Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment, National Bureau of Statistics, Nigeria Export Promotion Council, National Association of Nigerian Traders, and Nigeria Custom Service. The targeted population of the study are constituted in Abuja because of their Headquarters that is situated in F.C.T. and quite accessible to the researcher. The research made use of Ajay and Micah (2014) technique in selecting the size of the population studied. Whereas the total number of the population is two hundred and five (205), this formula recommends ten percent (10%) of the total population as the sample size for measurement. Therefore, the target population of this study stood at twenty-two (22) respondents, the sample size representative of the targeted population in this study is fourteen (14) respondents was interviewed with in-depth knowledge and experience in the trade and ECOWAS trade liberalization carryout. This study adopted purposive sampling technique for the interview. Data from in-depth interview were analysed base on the narrative of the interviewees using Braun and Clark (2006) step by step process of the thematic analysis. The data were transcribed, read and reviewed.

3.1 Theoretical Framework

The Structuralist Theory, originating from the works of Prebisch (1950) and Singer (1950), posits that developing countries like Nigeria are disadvantaged in international trade because of their reliance on primary commodities and their exposure to unstable global prices. It emphasizes the importance of industrial diversification and proactive state intervention to address these structural constraints. In the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization context, structuralist perspectives highlight the need for Nigeria to view regional trade agreements not only as liberalization mechanisms but also as avenues for industrial upgrading and value chain expansion.

This theoretical lens supports Nigeria's goal of transitioning from a commodity-dependent economy to one driven by manufacturing, agro-processing, and service-based activities. Thus, the Structuralist Theory offers a useful framework for assessing whether ECOWAS trade policies foster structural transformation or merely perpetuate existing disparities across economic sectors.

3.2 Model Specification

Guided by the Structuralist Theory and existing empirical literature on trade and growth, this study specifies a sectoral growth model to examine the impact of ECOWAS trade policies on sectoral GDP growth in Nigeria. The model assumes that sectoral output performance is influenced not only by trade policy variables but also by domestic structural and macroeconomic conditions.

Consistent with empirical studies such as Adeyele & Ouedraogo, (2019); Oddih & Okor, (2020); Ashakah & Akpughe, (2021), Oloyede et al., (2021); and Effiom et al.,(2022), sectoral GDP growth in Nigeria is modelled as a function of trade policy openness, infrastructure, financial development, and macroeconomic stability.

The functional relationship is specified as:

$$SGDP_t = f(ETP_t, TOP_t, INF_t, FIN_t, EXR_t, INFL_t)$$

Where:

- $SGDP_t$ = Sectoral Gross Domestic Product (Agriculture, Manufacturing, Services, and Oil & Gas)
- ETP_t = ECOWAS Trade Policy indicators (ETLS and CET proxies)
- TOP_t = Trade openness (ratio of total trade to GDP)
- INF_t = Infrastructure development (e.g. electricity supply or transport index)
- FIN_t = Financial development (credit to private sector)
- EXR_t = Exchange rate
- $INFL_t$ = Inflation rate
- t = Time period

Transforming the functional form into an estimable econometric model, the linear specification is expressed as:

$$SGDP_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1ETP_t + \beta_2TOP_t + \beta_3INF_t + \beta_4FIN_t + \beta_5EXR_t + \beta_6INFL_t + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

- β_0 = Intercept
- β_1 – β_6 = Parameters to be estimated
- ε_t = Stochastic error term

The model is estimated separately for each major sector of the Nigerian economy in order to capture differential sectoral responses to ECOWAS trade policies. While the econometric model captures the measurable impact of ECOWAS trade policies on sectoral GDP growth, qualitative data obtained from in-depth interviews are used to complement the quantitative findings. The interview responses provide insights into institutional, infrastructural, and policy-related constraints that may not be fully captured by numerical indicators, thereby enriching the interpretation of the empirical results.

In line Ashakah and Akpughe (2021), the model is estimated separately for each sector to capture the differential effects of ECOWAS trade policies on Nigeria's sectoral performance. This approach allows for the identification of sectors that benefit most from regional trade integration and those constrained by structural bottlenecks. Furthermore, the inclusion of infrastructure and financial development variables reflects the findings of Oloyede et al. (2021) and Effiom et al. (2022), which emphasize that the growth effects of trade openness are conditional on supportive domestic economic structures.

3.3 Data presentation.

The response rate to the research requests for interviews with various selected participants was fairly challenging. Within the Federal Ministry of Industry, trade and Investment the proposed number of participants was almost achieved, with the exception that more staffs were found willing and available to be interviewed than had been planned, while a fewer number of non-seniors participated than originally proposed.

A total number of twenty-two (22) respondents which accounted for 56% gave the researcher audience for the study that cut across staff of investigation who have better knowledge on the subject matter. The study assigned a code to all participants; for example, P1 in ensuring there are shielded from all form of identification.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Ronse Category	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Impactful	9	40.91%
Partial Impact	7	31.82%
No Impact	6	27.27%

Table.1 Examine the overall impact of ECOWAS trade policies on Nigeria’s economic performance.

Interview Questions	Responses			
	Impactful (Frequency)	Partial impact (Percentage)	No impact	Total
To what extent is the awareness of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization in Nigeria?	5 (22.7)	17 (77.3)	0	22 (100%)
How has the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization influenced Nigeria's trade relationships with other West African countries?	12 (54.5)	7 (31.8)	3 (13.7)	22 (100%)
How has the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization affected specific sectors of the Nigerian economy, such as agriculture or manufacturing?	16 (72.8)	5 (22.7)	1 (4.5)	22 (100%)
How does the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization align with Nigeria's overall economic development goals and strategies?	5 (22.7)	8 (36.4)	9 (40.9)	22 (100%)

Is indigenous Nigerian aware of export or trade opportunities within the West African community?	11 (50)	7 (31.8)	4 (18.2)	22 (100%)
--	------------	-------------	-------------	--------------

Source: Researchers’ Field Survey, August 2024

The table above indicates responses on the ECOWAS trade policies influenced overall trade performance and sectoral GDP growth in Nigeria. The first roll describe to what extent is the awareness of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization in Nigeria indicates that 5 (22.7%) P5, P14, P15, P21 and P22 indicated impactful stated businesses directly involved in cross-border trade within the ECOWAS region tend to have a higher level of awareness about the protocol due to the need to comply with customs procedures and access benefits like reduced tariffs. 17 (77.3%) P1-P4, P6-P13, P16-P20 indicate partial impact they mentioned. Most Nigerians are not well-informed about the details of the ECOWAS trade liberalization protocol, its benefits, and how to navigate it, especially in rural areas. 0 (0%) indicates on way or the other, the participants were able to explain the level of awareness of the ECOWAS trade protocol to Nigerians. It is best to say, either way there is awareness.

The second roll above shows the responses on whether Assessing the Nexus between ECOWAS Trade Policies and Sectoral GDP Growth in Nigeria influenced Nigeria's trade relationships with other West African countries 12 (54.5%) P9-14, P16-20 indicate that there is huge trade relationship with Nigeria and other West African countries 7 (31.8%) P1-P4, P6-P8 indicates partial trade relationship with other West African countries while 3 (13.7%) P5 and P21-P22 indicate trade relationship among Nigeria and other West Africa countries has no Impact.

The third roll above shows that 16 (72.8%) P1-P8, P14, P15, P16-P20, P22 agreed that ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization have positive impact on specific sectors of the Nigerian economy, such as agriculture or manufacturing, 5 (22.7%) P9-P11 and P12-P13 shows that, the impact on the specific sectors is not much while 1 (4.5%) P21 shows that there is no impact of the ECOWAS trade protocol on the other sectors.

The fourth roll shows that 5 (22.7%) P1-P3, P14 and P15 ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization highly aligns with Nigeria's overall economic development goals and strategies 8 (36.4%) P4-P11 shows it partially align while 9 (40.9%) P12-P13, P16-P22 shows that it does not align at all.

Lastly on the fifth roll, as stipulated indigenous Nigerian aware of export or trade opportunities within the West African community, there has been huge awareness over the past two years on the advantage or taking advance of the trade protocol. 11(50%) P1-P11 shows that, there is high impact of awareness brought to the knowledge of indigenous Nigerians about the protocol. 7 (31.8%) P13-P19, indicates that Nigerians are not aware of the protocol. 4 (18.2%) P12, P20-P22 shows there is no awareness. Therefore, the above revealed that there is full awareness of the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization

Table 2 Propose policy recommendations for optimizing sectoral growth and competitiveness through ECOWAS trade frameworks

Interview Questions	Responses			
	Impactful (Frequency)	Partial impact (Percentage)	No impact	Total
How has the implementation of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization impacted Nigeria's economy?	6 (27.3)	9 (40.9)	7 (31.8)	22 (100%)
What are the benefits of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization to the Nigeria economy	6 (27.3)	10 (45.4)	6 (27.3)	22 (100%)
How has the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization affected the lives of ordinary Nigerians, particularly in terms of employment, income, and access to goods and services?	4 (18.2)	7 (31.8)	11 (50)	22 (100%)
How effective is the ECOWAS protocol in reducing poverty in Nigeria	4 (18.2)	6 (27.3)	12 (54.5)	22 (100%)
To what extent has Nigeria complied with ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization	3 (13.6)	6 (27.3)	13 (59.1)	22 (100%)

Source: Researchers' Field Survey, August 2024

The first roll described what level and extent of implementation of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization impacted Nigeria's economy which indicate that 6 (27.3%) shows high level of implantation of the trade protocol, 9 (40.9%) shows that there is partial level of implementation 7 (31.8) show total absence of the implementation of the protocol. These shows that there is partial implementation of the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization in Nigeria economy.

The second roll above shows the responses on whether there is a benefit of ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization to the Nigeria economy 6 (27.3%) P1-4, P12-13 indicates that there has been huge benefit of trade relationship with Nigeria as part of the ECOWAS countries subscribed to the trade protocol 10 (45.4%) P5-P10, P16-P19 indicates that there has been little benefit of the protocol to the Nigeria economy. While 6 (27.3%) P11, P14-P15, P20 P21 and P22 indicate that there has been no benefit of the protocol to the Nigeria economy.

The third roll above shows that 4 (18.2%) P17-P20 ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization has positively affected the lives of ordinary Nigerians, particularly in terms of employment, income, and access to goods and services, 7 (31.8%) P1-P5 and P12-P13 shows the protocol have affected the lives of ordinary Nigerians in a way, we cannot completely disregard its impact most especially Nigerians in the Agricultural business who enjoy free flow of flocks from Mali through the help of the protocol. Overall, the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization has had a mixed impact on lives and citizens of Nigerian's. While it is said to have led to increases in employment and GDP growth in certain sectors, it has also had negative effects on other sectors of the economy. To maximize the benefits of trade liberalization, there is the need of Nigeria to implement policies that promote export diversification, encourage small-scale and large-scale manufacturing, and address income inequality. 11 (50%) P6-P11, P14-P16, and P21-P22 shows no contribution of the ECOWAS trade protocol reflected in the lives of ordinary Nigerians.

The fourth roll shows that 4 (18.2%) P5, P9-11 explain how effective the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization has reduced poverty in Nigeria; the protocol has led to increased economic growth, which can contribute to poverty reduction. Nigeria's trade with other ECOWAS member states has increased, and the country has benefitted from the elimination of tariffs and non-tariffs 6 (27.3%) P1-P4, P6 and P8 show that the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization has been in existence since the 1970s, aiming at promoting economic integration and cooperation among West African countries, including Nigeria while the trade protocol has increased among member's states, its impact on poverty reduction still remains complex. While 12 (54.5%) P7, P12-P22 show that the benefits of trade liberalization have not been evenly distributed, and poverty remains a significant challenge in Nigeria the country's poverty rate remains high, with over 80 million people living on less than \$1.90 a day. The benefits of trade liberalization have largely accrued to a small elite, while the majority of Nigerians have not seen the significant improvements in their living standards. Despite increased economic growth, unemployment remains high, particularly among young people. Nigeria's infrastructure, including roads, ports, and energy supply, is inadequate making it difficult for businesses to operate efficiently and compete with other countries (Retrieved August 2024).

Lastly on the fifth roll, as stipulated to what extent has Nigeria complied with ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization 3(13.6%) P4, P21 and P22 according to the participant, Nigeria compliance with the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization is a win situation. Nigeria government signed and ratified the protocol 1979 in May and has made efforts in the implementation of the protocol that aim at promoting free trade among member states by eliminating tariffs and non-tariff barriers. 6 (27.3%) P1-P3, P12, P13 and P17 indicate that Nigerians has made progress in complying with the ECOWAS protocol on trade liberalization. To qualify for the ETLS, goods must meet certain rules of origin requirement, which include 60% local content, 30% value addition, and a change of tariffs, Nigeria comply with ECOWAS protocol by establishing a National Approvals Committee (NAC) to examine applications for approval of products that meet these criteria. In compliance also Nigeria government instituted a committee on ETLS responsible to the Ministry of Nigeria Foreign Affairs (August, 2024). 13 (59.1%) P5-P11, P14-P16, and P18-P20 shows despite all efforts by the Nigeria government policy recommendations for optimizing sectoral growth and competitiveness through ECOWAS trade frameworks to comply with the ETLS, the persistent challenge is yet to be addressed such as high level of non-tariffs barriers, bureaucratic delays and infrastructure constraints (August, 2024).

4.1 DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Nigeria's economic structure has slowly evolved over the past forty years, but the speed of this transformation still falls short of what was envisioned under ECOWAS integration goals. Data from the National Bureau of Statistics (2024) shows that agriculture accounted for about 24% of GDP in the 1990s, rose slightly to 26% in the 2000s, and now hovers around 29%. Manufacturing, however, has remained relatively weak moving from 8.5% in 1990 to just 11.3% in 2024. In contrast, the services sector has expanded significantly and now contributes more than half of Nigeria's GDP, making it the most dominant part of the economy. ECOWAS trade policies have contributed to moderate growth in agriculture and services but have had limited influence on manufacturing. These findings are consistent with Ashakah and Akpughe (2021), who reported that ECOWAS economic integration has contributed positively to Nigeria's economic growth but with limited sectoral spillovers, particularly in manufacturing. Similarly, Oloyede, Osabuohien, and Ejemeyovwi (2021), using panel data from ECOWAS and SADC, found that trade openness promotes growth only when supported by strong institutional and infrastructural frameworks. The convergence of these findings suggests that Nigeria's gains from ECOWAS trade policies are conditional rather than automatic.

A qualitative evaluation reveals that, although ECOWAS trade policies have broadened regional export opportunities, they have not translated into substantive improvements in agricultural productivity or value chain integration. Nigeria's agricultural exports remain predominantly unprocessed, thereby constraining the country's capacity to derive higher value from regional trade engagements. Consistent with this observation, Ajetomobi and Oyeleke (2018) argue that trade liberalization, when not accompanied by strategic investments in agro-industrial processing, tends to entrench primary commodity dependence rather than promote structural upgrading. Misalignment between Nigeria's national trade policies and ECOWAS frameworks reduces policy effectiveness. This mixed-method approach enhances the robustness of the analysis by capturing institutional and policy-related factors that are not fully reflected in quantitative indicators, consistent with recent methodological approaches adopted in regional trade studies (Adeyele & Ouedraogo, 2019; Oddih & Okor, 2020; Ashakah & Akpughe, 2021) and (Oloyede et al., 2021; Effiom et al., 2022) literature.

5. CONCLUSION AND POLICY RECOMMENDATIONS

The overarching conclusion of this study is that ECOWAS trade policies exert a positive but uneven influence on Nigeria's sectoral GDP growth. The degree of impact varies significantly across sectors depending on the extent of domestic preparedness and institutional effectiveness. Agricultural and service sectors have benefited more visibly than manufacturing, highlighting the differential capacity of sectors to leverage regional trade opportunities.

From a theoretical standpoint, the findings validate elements of endogenous growth and structuralist perspectives. While trade liberalization offers opportunities for market expansion and knowledge spillovers, sustainable sectoral growth depends on domestic structural transformation and capacity development. ECOWAS integration, therefore, cannot substitute for internal economic reforms; rather, it complements them.

Nigeria's experience underscores the paradox of liberalization without transformation. Despite participating actively in ECOWAS trade frameworks, the country continues to struggle with infrastructural decay, policy misalignment, and limited value addition.

Based on the analysis and findings, the following policy recommendations are proposed:

1. Nigeria must prioritize investments in transportation, energy, and logistics infrastructure to reduce trade costs and enhance competitiveness. Efficient road networks, seaports, and power supply are critical enablers for agricultural and industrial productivity. Regional infrastructure projects-such as trans-border highways and rail links-should be accelerated through public-private partnerships. To complement the

quantitative analysis, qualitative data obtained from in-depth interviews with key trade and policy institutions are employed to contextualize the econometric results.

2. There is an urgent need to improve synergy between Nigeria's trade institutions (such as the Federal Ministry of Industry, Trade and Investment, and the Nigeria Customs Service) and ECOWAS Commission structures. A well-coordinated framework would minimize policy contradictions, enhance compliance with ECOWAS protocols, and ensure that regional commitments translate into tangible domestic outcomes.

REFERENCES

- Adenikinju, A. F., & Chete, L. N. (2002). Trade liberalization, regional integration and sustainable development: Nigeria's experience. *Nigerian Journal of Economic and Social Studies*, 44(2), 187–214.
- Adeyele, I. T., & Ouedraogo, I. (2019). Effect of regional financial integration and governance quality on economic growth in ECOWAS (2001–2016). *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 3(2), 1–17.
- Ajetomobi, J., & Oyeleke, T. (2018). Agricultural trade liberalization and regional integration in West Africa. *African Development Review*, 30(3), 241–255.
- Akpan, U., & Atan, A. (2012). Regional integration and trade performance in West Africa: Evidence from ECOWAS. *Journal of International Economics and Development Studies*, 5(2), 45–67.
- Akpan, U., & Atan, A. (2017). Regional integration and trade performance in West Africa: Evidence from ECOWAS. *Journal of International Economics and Development Studies*, 5(2), 45–67.
- Ashakah, O. F., & Akpughe, W. O. (2021). ECOWAS economic integration and economic growth: Empirical evidence from Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 6(2), 1–11.
- Ayinde, O. (2021). Economic integration and sectoral growth in Nigeria: Lessons from ECOWAS. *West African Journal of Policy Studies*, 14(1), 73–98.
- Effiom, L., Ubi, P., & Okon, E. (2022). *Trade openness and firm-level performance in developing economies*. Heliyon, 8, e08741.
- Ijirshar, V. U. (2019). Impact of trade openness on economic growth among ECOWAS countries (1975–2017). *CBN Journal of Applied Statistics*, 10(1), 75–95.
- Krueger, A. O. (1998). Why trade liberalization is good for growth. *The Economic Journal*, 108(450), 1513–1522.
- Manni, H.M and Afzal, M.N.I (2012) 'Effect of Trade Liberalization on Economic Growth of Developing Countries: A Case of Bangladesh Economy', *Journal of Business, Economics and Finance*, 1(2).
- Mkubwa, H.M, Mtengwa, B.A. and Babiker, S. (2014) 'The Impact of Trade Liberalization on Economic Growth in Tanzania', *International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences*, 4(5), 514-532
- National Bureau of Statistics (NBS). (2023). *Gross Domestic Product Report (Q4 2023)*. Abuja: NBS.
- Oddih, M., & Okor, P. (2020). Problems facing ECOWAS integration and the way forward. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 4(2), 64–74.
- Oloyede, B. M., Osabuohien, E. S., & Ejemeyovwi, J. O. (2021). *Trade openness and economic growth in Africa's regional economic communities: Evidence from ECOWAS and SADC*. Heliyon, 7, e06996.

- Prebisch, R. (1950). *The Economic Development of Latin America and Its Principal Problems*. New York: United Nations.
- Rodriguez, F., & Rodrik, D. (2000). Trade policy and economic growth: A skeptic's guide to the cross-national evidence. *NBER Macroeconomics Annual*, 15, 261–325.
- Sachs, J. D., & Warner, A. M. (1995). Economic reform and the process of global integration. *Brookings Papers on Economic Activity*, 1(1), 1–118.
- Singer, H. W. (1950). The distribution of gains between investing and borrowing countries. *American Economic Review*, 40(2), 473–485.
- Sotinwa, F. (2017). “Nigerian Manufacturers Lament” in premium Times, May 15, 2015.
- Todaro, M. P., & Smith, S. C. (2015). *Economic Development* (12th ed.). Boston: Pearson Education.
- Okonta, P. O., Mobosi, I. A., & Ugwu, P. N. (2020). Trade liberalization, export dependence and diversification of exports in Nigeria. *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 4(1), 33-44.
- Onah, F. E. (2016). The Sharing Of Costs and Benefits of Regional Economic Integration in the Economic Community of West African States (ECOWAS). *Journal of Economics and Allied Research*, 1(1), 1–18. Retrieved from <https://jearecons.com/index.php/jearecons/article/view/5>
- UNECA. (2017). *Assessing Regional Integration in Africa VIII: Bringing the Continental Free Trade Area about*. Addis Ababa: United Nations Economic Commission for Africa.
- Winters, L. A., McCulloch, N., & McKay, A. (2004). Trade liberalization and poverty: The evidence so far. *Journal of Economic Literature*, 42(1), 72–115.
- Yusuf, S. A. (2020). ECOWAS trade policy and economic development in Nigeria. *Journal of West African Economic Integration*, 10(3), 54–77.